

Key Results from Monitoring & Evaluation

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PROGRAM REACH

5

Satellite Sites
across Peel

8

Peer Satellite
Workers

33

Advisory members
engaged

3646

Client service sessions
delivered

691

People accessed
services

We collected surveys from 306 People Who Use Drugs (PWUD) that had accessed our sites:

36% Women

23% Under 34 years old

33% Had never used other services

TOP 5 REASONS FOR ACCESSING THE SITE

- 1 I know the person who lives here and trust them (57%)
- 2 It's anonymous here (55%)
- 3 This location is closer to me than other places (54%)
- 4 I can come here during hours that work for me (46%)
- 5 I just want a safe place to hang out (30%)

TYPE OF SERVICES USED

- 1 Harm reduction and sexual health supplies (85%)
- 2 Information about other community services (36%)
- 3 Education (e.g. overdose prevention, sexual health) (33%)
- 4 Counselling (32%)
- 5 Other (21%)

VOICES FROM THE COMMUNITY

“ I feel like my life experience is worth value here and makes sense not just to waste it on regrets [...]. My past brings worthy value as it opens doors for me when I I never thought could be possible, bringing opportunities to provide support to others along the way. — Program Participant

“ Being an advisor has broadened my knowledge on infections and diseases as well as what it takes to be an affective harm reduction worker which is a goal for my future. — Program Participant

MOYO'S POLICY & ADVOCACY FOOTPRINT

CHAIRS

Peel Harm Reduction Committee

CO-CHAIRS

Peel Substance Strategy

Peel Drug Toxicity Urgent Response Plan

Ontario AIDS Network's HR Policy/Advocacy Working Group

SUPPORTS / PARTICIPATES

Encampment Policy & Protocols Steering Committee & Working Group

Peel Drug Users Advisory Panel (Lived Experience Input)

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